

RES4LIVE

ENERGY SMART LIVESTOCK FARMING
TOWARDS ZERO FOSSIL FUEL CONSUMPTION

Web site and social media presence

Deliverable 7.1

WP7. Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation

Project title

RES4LIVE - Energy Smart Livestock Farming towards Zero Fossil Fuel Consumption

Grant agreement: 101000785

From 1st October 2020 to 30th September 2024

Prepared by: EAAP

30/12/2020

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Deliverable Factsheet

Deliverable no.	Deliverable D7.1: Web site and social media presence
Responsible Partner	EAAP
WP no. and title	7: Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation
Task no. and title	7.1: Dissemination and Communication Plan and activities
Version	1
Version Date	30/12/20

Dissemination level	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU = Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC)
<input type="checkbox"/>	RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC)
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)

Approvals/ Document history

	Company
Author/s	EAAP
Task Leader	EUREC
WP Leader	CETRI

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PARTNERS SHORT NAMES

AUA - AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS

UNIBO – UNIVERSITY OF BOLOGNA

ATB - AGRICULTURAL ENGINEERING AND BIOECONOMY

EV ILVO - AGRICULTURAL AND FISHERIES RESEARCH

UGENT - GHENT UNIVERSITY

CERTH - CENTRE FOR RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY-HELLAS

AU - AARHUS UNIVERSITY

LVAT - LEHR- UND VERSUCHSANSTALT FÜR TIERZUCHT UND TIERHALTUNG GROß KREUTZ E.V.

PSYCTOTHERM - G. LIGEROS & SIA OE

PLEGMA LABS- PLEGMA LABS TECHNOLOGIKES LYSEIS ANONYMOS ETAIRIA

CRMT SAS - CENTRE DE RECHERCHES EN MACHINES THERMIQUES

TERRA - TERRA ENERGY

MG SUSTAINABLE - MG SUSTAINABLE ENGINEERING AB

CETRI - CENTER FOR TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH & INNOVATION LTD

GOLINELLI - GOLINELLI GIULIO

EAAP - FEDERAZIONE EUROPEA PER LA ZOOTECNICA

EUREC - EUREC EESV

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

Deliverable D7.1 entails to the creation and the development of the project’s public website (www.res4live.eu), and installation of social media channels, which will be used as the main instruments to present the project objectives/structure and its consortium and activities.

The RES4LIVE website is the major communication tool of the project, intended to facilitate the spread of project information to different stakeholder groups, such as national and international Livestock farming organizations and relative industries, renewable energy associations, energy systems manufacturers, environmental organizations, policy-makers, research and innovation networks, media, society at large and other stakeholders, as well as scientists outside RES4LIVE consortium.

The main purpose of the website and the social media channels is to raise awareness about the project activities, to inform about the aims, the ongoing research and innovation activities, trainings, events and publications. A second purpose of the website is to assist with dissemination of project outputs in order to encourage feedback from stakeholders and to promote the spreading and exploitation of project results.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The RES4LIVE website and social media are part of Task 7.1 “Dissemination and communication plan and activities” dealing with the planning of project communication and dissemination activities. It is led by EUREC to be carried out within Work Package (WP) 7, which is led by CETRI.

EAAP will take care of constantly updating the RES4LIVE website and animating the project social media.

The RES4LIVE website is the major communication and dissemination tool of the project, intended to facilitate the targeted spread of project information to different stakeholder groups.

The website and interactive social media channels will support the possibility of contacting RES4LIVE parties.

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2 WEBSITE

The RES4LIVE website has been created by EAAP, who provided technical support in the hosting and development of the website in close interaction with the project coordinator, AUA and the WP leader, CETRI.

The official registration of the domain name is: <http://www.res4live.eu/>. The site will be operative from 31st December 2020.

The structure, design and functionalities of the web interface were identified and agreed by EAAP and AUA. All partners will actively collaborate to update it, whenever necessary. The website is a platform for interaction with stakeholders ranging from policy makers, industrial stakeholders to the interested public and society at large. All public information generated in the project will be easily findable and accessible. This is achieved by a coordinated and conclusive website structure, which places items for fast information uptake in prominent positions to achieve high visibility. The special feature of the website is the activity & news box, in which short news entries can be posted easily, linking the visitors to events, publications, press releases and other project related information. In a second box tweets are visualized and linked. The RES4LIVE initial entry Homepage is structured according to the following sections (see Annex 1 for screenshots of the website):

ITEM	CONTENT
Home page	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facts and figures about the project • Navigation tabs • Links to social media • Activity news box • Dedicated box for visualizing Tweets (Twitter) • Events box • RES4LIVE newsletter subscribe button
Project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenge • Objectives • Expected impact • Structure
Partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partners list with logos and links to websites
Communication and Dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peer reviewed publications • Conferences • Videos • Photo gallery (Project-related photos organized per event) • Press releases • Promotional material • RES4LIVE newsletter archive
Stakeholders engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Case studies

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clustering with other projects • Pilot farm workshops • Inventory of best practices
Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List of RES4LIVE related events
Access to RES4LIVE intranet	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Restricted collaborative workspace for project partners)

2.1 RES4LIVE Intranet

From the home page it is possible to access a restricted collaborative workspace to upload and download internal project-related documents. Access to this workspace will be given to project participants only and it is password-protected. All partners can upload/download documents, while only EAAP, as administrators, and AUA, as project coordinator can delete documents. For the moment, the overall available capacity is 10 Gigabyte with the possibility of further increase, while there is a limit of 20 MB for any single file.

The workspace was developed in close collaboration with AUA and is currently structured in folders and subfolders as follows:

- Contractual documents
- Confidential deliverables
- Milestones verification
- Project meetings (draft agendas, presentations, minutes)
- Templates for targeted public and media material
- Work packages space (each subdivided in tasks, for internal document exchanges).

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3 SOCIAL MEDIA STRATEGY AND MANAGEMENT

In a first instance, RES4LIVE will use four different social media networks to target different stakeholder groups: Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube. Facebook is the most popular social network when targeting end-users in many of the European countries. Twitter and LinkedIn are mostly used by companies, researchers and by international, national and local policy and decision makers. Twitter is largely used by different umbrella organizations representing different parts of the society, from producers to consumers. LinkedIn is mainly targeting professionals willing to read more about technological and knowledge advances and enables users to connect and share content with other professionals. YouTube is used to share all kinds of audio-visual information for a broad range of stakeholders from the general public to scientists.

The social media strategy of RES4LIVE aims at:

- Attracting many different target groups and stakeholders;
- Raising awareness on the activities RES4LIVE is conducting;
- Spreading news/content about the project: project content, activities, news, results etc.;
- Engaging social media users and directing them to the RES4LIVE website.

In order to achieve the aims of the RES4LIVE social media strategy, the actions listed below are being carried out;

- Sharing targeted social media posts to inform about the progress of the project, events, news and results;
- Using social media channels to actively engage with relevant stakeholders;
- Preparation of targeted social media campaigns.

RES4LIVE social media accounts (see Annex 2 for screenshots of the website):

SOCIAL MEDIA CHANNEL	ACCOUNT LINK
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/RES4LIVE
Twitter	https://twitter.com/RES4LIVE (@RES4LIVE)
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/res4live-project/
YouTube	To be open soon

All partners are encouraged to follow and share the above accounts. In order to engage a wider audience through social media, their content must be relevant, valuable and usable for the different target groups. Different kinds of content could (among others) be;

- Publication of research results
- Presentation at conferences
- Writing articles
- Publication of informative videos

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- Pictures and videos
- Promoting RES4LIVE or other interesting events.

The social media accounts can also be used to participate in discussions on relevant social platforms.

Preliminary relevant Hashtags and tags:

HASHTAGS	MENTIONS FOR TWITTER
#H2020	@EU_Commission
#livestock	@RES4LIVE
#agriculture	@EAAPofficial
#sustainability	@EUREC_Info
#renewableenergy	@ILVOvlaanderen
#decarbonization	@ugent
#fossilfree	@AarhusUni

In order to make full use of the communication channels, it is important to harmonize and integrate the contents of the different social media channels by:

- enabling the sharing of the RES4LIVE website content
- embedding Twitter feed on the homepage of the RES4LIVE website
- giving the links to the social media channels in the RES4LIVE newsletter
- promoting the RES4LIVE activities or related events via the social media accounts.

Annex 1

RES4LIVE Home page

Home Project Partners Communication & Dissemination Stakeholder engagement Events Restricted Area

Photo Copyright: © Manuel Gutjahr

RES4LIVE will and bring into the market integrated cost effective and case sensitive Renewable Energy Sources (RES) solutions towards achieving fossil free livestock farming.

It involves 17 partners from 8 countries. The consortium is made of 4 Universities, 4 Research Organizations, 6 SMEs, 1 Farm and 2 International Associations.

RES4LIVE will last 48 months from 1st October 2020 to 30th September 2024 with a budget of 4.998.455,00 €

The strategic objective of RES4LIVE is to develop and bring into the market integrated, cost-effective and case-sensitive RES solutions towards achieving fossil-free livestock farming

RES and machinery adaptation, and other technologies selection.

Pilot systems design, installation and testing.

Multi-level Assessment: technical, economic, social, environmental.

Replicability and impact generation: case studies, clustering, stakeholders' engagement etc.

Learn more about the Project

Activity News

The H2020 RES4LIVE project (2020-2024) has started!
December 29, 2020
The Kick-off meeting of the H2020 RES4LIVE project: "Energy Smart Livestock Farming towards Zero Fossil Fuel Consumption" was held via teleconference – to comply with
[Read More >](#)

[All news](#)

Tweets

6 days ago

[Read More >>](#)

1 month ago

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Events

There are no upcoming events.

[All events](#)

12

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Partners

RES4LIVE
ENERGY SMART LIVESTOCK FARMING
TOWARDS ZERO FOSSIL FUEL CONSUMPTION

Project Framework
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Project
Newsletter
Restricted Area

Contacts
Privacy Policy
Cookie policy

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RES4LIVE Challenge page

 [Subscribe the Newsletter](#)

- [Home](#)
- [Project](#) ▾
- [Partners](#)
- [Communication & Dissemination](#) ▾
- [Stakeholder engagement](#) ▾
- [Events](#)
- [Restricted Area](#)

Challenge

Fossil fuel use in the agricultural domain has negative effects becoming a major source of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, with significant contributions to global climate change and the risk of food security. One of the most energy-consuming sub-sectors of agriculture is intensive livestock that is mainly based on fossil fuels use. However, more sustainable livestock production and de-fossilising energy needs in husbandry facilities emerge as crucial aspects within EU.

With declining costs and improvement of reliability and performance of key renewable energy sources (RES) technologies (e.g. PVs, heat pumps, biogas), the opportunities for farmers and specifically for livestock producers to engage in RES production are increasing, and new business models are emerging on the market.

The above, create specific challenges for the individual farmer including the need for sound advice, investment support and risk management. The adaptation of RES technologies and machinery and their demonstration at a large-scale on farm level require supporting measures with respect to spatial planning, infrastructure, different business models and market organisation, trends that are not all under control from a farmers' perspective. RES4LIVE project will fill these gaps ensuring a wider adoption of RES and energy efficiency technologies, machinery and techniques in livestock farms towards a zero-fossil fuel consumption. The project activities at a glance are highlighted in the figure below.

- [Project](#)
- [Newsletter](#)
- [Restricted Area](#)

- [Contacts](#)
- [Privacy Policy](#)
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Project Framework
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RES4LIVE Structure page

 [Subscribe the Newsletter](#)

- [Home](#)
- [Project](#) ▾
- [Partners](#)
- [Communication & Dissemination](#) ▾
- [Stakeholder engagement](#) ▾
- [Events](#)
- [Restricted Area](#)

Structure

To achieve all specific objectives of RES4LIVE towards de-fossilising industrial livestock farming 8 Work Packages (WPs) will undertake the required actions, as shown in the Pert chart below.

[Project](#)
[Newsletter](#)
[Restricted Area](#)

[Contacts](#)
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Annex 2

RES4LIVE Facebook page

The screenshot displays the Facebook profile for RES4LIVE. The profile name is RES4LIVE (@RES4LIVE · Community) with a blue 'Send Message' button. Navigation tabs include Home, Reviews, About, Videos, and More. The 'About' section states: 'RES4LIVE is a H2020-funded project whose strategic objective is to develop and bring into the market integrated, cost-effective and case-sensitive RES solutions towards achieving fossil-free livestock farming. Grant agreement no. 101000785.' It shows 20 likes and 22 followers. A 'Suggest edits' section asks if the page has a phone number. The 'Photos' section shows a 'HAPPY HOLIDAYS' post with the text 'WISHING YOU ALL HAPPY HOLIDAYS'. The post has 2 likes and options to Like, Comment, and Share.

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RES4LIVE Twitter page

RES4LIVE
@RES4LIVE

RES4LIVE is a H2020-funded project which supports Energy Smart Livestock Farming towards Zero Fossil Fuel Consumption. Grant agreement no. 101000785.

Joined November 2020

7 Following 24 Followers

RES4LIVE LinkedIn page

RES4LIVE
ENERGY SMART LIVESTOCK FARMING
TOWARDS ZERO FOSSIL FUEL CONSUMPTION

RES4LIVE Project
Agricoltura - ATHENS - 523 follower

Energy Smart Livestock Farming towards Zero Fossil Fuel Consumption

Visita sito web

Informazioni

The adaptation of RES technologies and machinery and their demonstration at a large-scale on farm level, require supporting measures with respect to spatial planning, infrastructure, different business models and market orga... vedi altro

Vedi tutti

Tutto Immagini Documenti Video

Ordina per: In alto

Annunci

RES4LIVE Project
523 follower
7m • Modificato •

RES4LIVE's goal is to develop and bring into the market integrated, cost-effective and case-sensitive RES solutions towards achieving fossil-free livestock farming. In this context, the project will focus on increasing the overall sustainability of four pilot farms. More info & insights will follow soon! #sustainability #renewableenergies #agriculture #livestock ...vedi altro

Consiglia Commenta Condividi Invia

Scrivi tu il primo commento

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+ Segui

Res4Venture
Investment Banking
+ Segui

DITECT Project EU/China